

Condensation of Phenols and Phenolic Ethers with Acetone Dicarboxylic Acid. Part I. β -Substituted Glutaconic Acids.

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The preliminary portion of this work was done by the author in co-operation with D. B. Limaye, (*vide*, *Proc. Indian Science Congress*, 1930, p. 167). Limaye and Bhave (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 137), showed the formation of β -4-methoxyphenyl glutaconic acid when anisole is condensed with acetone dicarboxylic acid and studied some of its reactions. The present work is an extension of this reaction to phenol and *o*-cresolmethyl ether and deals with the establishment of the constitution of the products obtained, by direct syntheses as also several new and interesting reactions and changes which the β -substituted glutaconic acids undergo. Besides the usual dibasic acid as found by Limaye and Bhave (*loc. cit.*), a monobasic ketonic acid of which an account will be given in part II of this series, is also formed in these reactions.

The constitution of the dibasic acids as advanced by the foregoing authors, *viz.*, $\text{R}^*\text{C}:\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{H}$ has been confirmed by the

$$\begin{array}{c} | \\ \text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{H} \end{array}$$

following syntheses —

(1) from the corresponding glutaric ester (*cf.* Darbishire and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 1714);

and (2) from the corresponding benzoylacetate ester (Thole and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 99, 2187).

* C occupying the *para* position to the hydroxy or methoxy group.

The glutaconic acids described in this paper have therefore the following constitution.

It is evident that the reduction products of the glutaconic acids should be the corresponding glutaric acids. The three glutaconic acids were therefore reduced by sodium amalgam in alkaline solution. The resulting glutaric acids, which are new, were prepared by two following synthetical processes: (a) condensation of *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of *p*-hydroxybenzylidenedipiperidyl and subsequent hydrolysis of the condensation product (Kotz, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1907, ii, 75, 515), and (b) condensation of ethyl *p*-hydroxycinnamate with ethyl cyanoacetate and subsequent hydrolysis of the condensation product (Thorpe and Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 75, 52). They have therefore the following constitution.

When reduced by phosphorus and hydriodic acid, compound from phenol gave ultimately cumol or *p*-hydroxyisopropylbenzene. Similar derivatives were obtained from other compounds. Each glutaric acid on heating with sodalime, eliminated two molecules of carbon dioxide and gave a cumol derivative. Such elimination of carbon dioxide from the glutaconic acids take place in stages on heating with water in a sealed tube, and immediately when boiled with 5 p.c. hydrochloric acid.

Glutaconic acid.

β -Substituted
crotonic acid.

iso Propenylbenzene.

On melting, the acids eliminated one molecule of water and produced a monobasic ketonic acid identical with that obtained in the original

condensation (*loc. cit.*). Acetyl chloride acts on them in the same way. Further work in this connection will be described in the next part. The semianilides, which the acids gave with aniline, lost one molecule of water at the melting point, giving anhydrides which formed compounds with semicarbazide. The glutaconic acids absorbed two atoms of bromine when worked according to the method of Verkade and Coops (jun.) (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1920, 39, 586). The *laevo*-rotatory dibromide $R \cdot CBr \cdot CHBr \cdot CO_2H$ was isolated from the *racemic* com-

$$\begin{array}{c} | \\ CH_2 \cdot CO_2H \end{array}$$

pound through the brucine salt. The reaction between cyanoacetic ester and the glutaconic ester as carried out according to the method of Kohler and Reid (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 2803) resulted in the formation of a *p*-substituted phenylmethane triacetic acid of the general formula $R \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot C(CH_2 \cdot CO_2H)_3$. The semiammonium salts of the acids distilled after Rogerson and Thorpe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 1691), gave corresponding pyridine derivatives. The nature of the reaction is under investigation.

On fusing the β -4-methoxyphenylglutaconic acid with potassium hydroxide at 200°, a substituted acetophenone and a phenylacetic acid were obtained.

The β -4-methoxyphenylglutaconic acid, when acted upon by 30 p.c. hydrogen peroxide in acetic acid solution, gave the methyl ether of the hydroxyphenylacetic acid identical with that obtained from potash fusion.

EXPERIMENTAL.

β-4-Hydroxyphenylglutaconic acid from (a) phenol and acetone dicarboxylic acid.—Powdered citric acid (25 g.) was heated with 95 p. c. sulphuric acid (75 g.) at 66° to 70° for half an hour with shaking at intervals. After cooling the mixture below 5°, phenol (10 g.) was gradually added to it with shaking, keeping the temperature below 10°. After two hours the mixture was poured over ice and allowed to stand for about three hours in a refrigerator. The glutaconic acid separated as a heavy reddish powder which was collected and washed with small quantities of sodium chloride solution. The powder was dissolved in 10 p. c. sodium hydroxide solution and was converted into its barium salt. The salt was collected, washed with little alcohol, dried and decomposed by 10 p.c. hydrochloric acid. The acid which separated on cooling, was filtered, washed and crystallised from a small quantity of water as colourless prismatic crystals, m.p. 184° (decomp.); yield 1.6 g. (Found: Eq. wt., 111.2; C, 59.42; H, 4.81. $C_{11}H_{10}O_5$ requires Eq. wt., 111; C, 59.44; H, 4.55 per cent.). Barium salt: (Found: Ba, 38.15. $C_{11}H_8O_5$ Ba requires Ba, 38.35 per cent.).

(b) From the corresponding glutaric ester (Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 1714).—Diethyl-*β*-4-hydroxyphenylglutarate was brominated by the method of Thorpe (*loc. cit.*) to ethyl *α*-bromo-*β*-4-hydroxyphenylglutarate; thick brown liquid, b.p. 230°/21mm. yield 40 p. c. (Found: Br, 21.42. $C_{15}H_{19}O_5Br$ requires Br, 21.23 per cent.). This was then converted into the glutaconic acid by the method of Thorpe (*loc. cit.*), m.p. 180° (decomp.), yield 15 p. c. Mixed m.p. with the acid obtained in (a), 182° (decomp.).

(c) From ethyl *p*-hydroxybenzoylacetate.—On condensing this with ethyl cyanoacetate according to the method of Thorpe (*loc. cit.*) ethyl *α*-cyano-*β*-4-hydroxyphenylglutaconate was obtained as thick yellowish liquid, b.p. 269°/18mm., yield 50 p.c. (Found: C, 63.15; H, 5.55. $C_{16}H_{17}O_5N$ requires C, 63.27; H, 5.62 per cent.). This compound was then hydrolysed according to the method of Thorpe (*loc. cit.*) to the glutaconic acid, m.p. 184° (decomp.), yield 12 p. c. ; Eq. wt., 111.3; mixed m.p. with the acid obtained in (a), 184° (decomp.).

β-4-Acetoxyphenylglutaconic acid was prepared by heating *β*-4-hydroxyphenylglutaconic acid (5 g.) with acetic anhydride (15 c.c) on a boiling water-bath. It formed rectangular prisms from ethyl acetate,

m.p. 193° (decomp.), yield 4.2 g. (Found: Eq. wt., 132.2; C, 59.2; H, 4.51. $C_{13}H_{12}O_6$ requires Eq. wt., 132; C, 59.09; H, 4.54 per cent.). *Barium salt*: (Found: Ba, 34.5. $C_{13}H_{10}O_6$ Ba requires Ba, 34.33 per cent.).

Diethyl-β-4-hydroxyphenylglutaconate.—An alcoholic solution of the glutaconic acid (10 g. in 50. c.c.) was refluxed with sulphuric acid (15 g.) on a boiling water-bath for two hours. After removal of alcohol, the residue was diluted with water and the oil which separated was extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with soda solution, dried over calcium chloride and distilled; b.p. 268°/25 mm., yield 10.2 g. (Found: C, 64.88; H, 6.39. $C_{15}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 64.75; H, 6.47 per cent.).

β-4-Hydroxyphenylglutaric Acid.

(a) *Reduction of the corresponding glutaconic acid*.—Freshly prepared sodium amalgam (1.7 g. sodium in 70 g. mercury) in small pieces, was added gradually to a *N*-caustic soda solution of β-4-hydroxyphenylglutaconic acid (5 g. in 40 c.c.) and the mixture shaken well after each addition, the whole addition being completed within 45 minutes. The mixture was then allowed to stand for one hour (air being excluded) when the mercury separated from it. The mixture was concentrated, boiled with animal charcoal and filtered. The solid which separated on acidifying the filtrate, was converted into the copper salt by means of copper acetate and the glutaric acid liberated by the decomposition of the copper salt by acid; white prisms from water, m.p. 172°, yield 4.4 g. It gave a greenish blue coloration with ferric chloride. (Found: Eq. wt., 111.7; C, 58.85; H, 5.3. $C_{11}H_{12}O_5$ requires Eq. wt., 112; C, 59.00; H, 5.35 per cent.).

(b) *From p-hydroxybenzaldehyde* (Method of Kotz, *loc. cit.*).—*p-Hydroxybenzylidenedipiperidyl*, white prisms from ligroin, m.p. 112°, yield, theoretical. (Found: N, 10.31. $C_{17}H_{26}ON_2$ requires N, 10.2 per cent.).

p-Hydroxybenzylidenebisacetoacetic ester.—White crystals from alcohol, m.p. 136°, yield 80 p. c. (Found: C, 62.6; H, 6.5. $C_{19}H_{24}O_7$ requires C, 62.7; H, 6.6 per cent.). The glutaric acid, melted at 168°, yield 25 per cent. Mixed m.p. with the acid obtained in (a), 170°.

(c) *From ethyl -p-hydroxycinnamate* (Method of Perkin and Thorpe, *loc. cit.*).—*Ethyl-α-cyano-β-4-hydroxyphenylglutarate*, pale

yellow liquid, b.p. $184^{\circ}/16$ mm., yield 60 p. c. (Found: C, 62.7; H, 6.1. $C_{16}H_{19}O_5N$ requires C, 62.9; H, 6.2 per cent.). The glutaric acid, m.p. 171.5° , yield 20 per cent. Mixed m.p. with the acid obtained in (a), 172° .

Diethyl- β -4-hydroxyphenylglutarate.—An alcoholic solution of the corresponding glutaric acid (5 g. in 35 c.c. of absolute alcohol) was saturated with dry hydrochloric acid gas and refluxed in dry atmosphere on a water-bath for four hours. The alcohol was removed and the residue distilled directly; b.p. $268^{\circ}/18$ mm., yield, 4.6 g. (Found: C, 64.16; H, 7.1. $C_{15}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 64.3; H, 7.14 per cent.).

p-Hydroxyisopropylbenzene or Cumol.

(a) *From the corresponding glutaric acid*.—An intimate mixture of powdered sodalime and *β -4-hydroxyphenylglutaric acid* (5 g.) was heated gently in a tubular retort, the volatile portion being collected in a small well cooled receiver. On keeping the receiver in a refrigerator, the contents solidified; short needles from petroleum ether, m.p. 61° , yield 1 g. The aqueous solution gave a blue coloration with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 79.5; H, 8.75. $C_9H_{12}O$ requires C, 79.4; H, 8.84 per cent.).

(b) *By reduction of the glutaconic acid*.—Red phosphorus (1.5 g.) was added in small quantities to a mixture of *β -4-hydroxyphenylglutaconic acid* (4 g.), glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.) and hydroiodic acid (13 g. of 4 p. c.) and the mixture refluxed for one hour. It was cooled, diluted, neutralised by sodium carbonate and filtered. The residue on the filter on extraction with ether gave cumol; m.p. 59.5° , yield 1.2 g. Mixed m.p. with the cumol obtained in (a), 60° .

β -4-Hydroxyphenylcrotonic acid.— *β -4-Hydroxyphenylglutaconic acid* (7.5 g.) was heated with water (15 c.c.) in a sealed tube at 150° in an oil-bath for eight hours. On opening the tube, the contents were mixed with 10 p. c. sodium carbonate solution and distilled with steam until no volatile portion came over. The residual mixture was filtered, concentrated, boiled with animal charcoal and acidified. The solid crotonic acid which separated, gave prismatic plates from alcohol, m.p. 163° , yield 2.8 g. (Found: Eq. wt., 177.1; C, 67.5; H, 5.6. $C_{10}H_{10}O_3$ requires Eq. wt., 178; C, 67.4; H, 5.62 per cent.).

The volatile portion on purification was identified with *p*-hydroxy-isopropenylbenzene, m.p. 59°, yield 1 g.; benzoyl derivative m.p. 127°.

Semianilide of β -4-hydroxyphenylglutaconic acid.—A mixture of the glutaconic acid (11 g.) and dry aniline (6 g.) was refluxed at 140° in an oil-bath for eight hours. The pasty mass which separated on pouring the cold mixture into excess of hydrochloric acid (5 p. c.) became solid on grinding repeatedly with the dilute acid. It was then dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution and filtered. The product, precipitated on acidifying the filtrate, was washed, dried and crystallised from glacial acetic acid; long yellow prisms, m.p. 197° (decomp.), yield 12.1 g. (Found: Eq. wt., 295.8; N, 4.62. $C_{17}H_{15}O_4N$ requires Eq. wt., 297; N, 4.71 per cent.).

$\alpha\beta$ -Dibromo- β -4-methoxyphenylglutaric Acid.

(a) The method of Verkade and Coops (*loc. cit.*), gave colourless plates from alcohol, m.p. 121°, yield 78 p. c. (Found: Eq. wt., 197.6; Br, 40.32. $C_{12}H_{12}O_5Br_2$ requires Eq. wt., 198; Br, 40.4 per cent.).

(b) Bromine vapour (4.5 g.) was sucked through a solution of β -4-methoxyphenylglutaconic acid (6 g.) in glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.) by means of a water-pump. The pasty mass which separated on distilling the solution with water, solidified on washing with dilute alcohol; colourless plates from alcohol, m.p. 119°, yield 3 g.

(c) *The optically active antipode.*—A mixture of the alcoholic solutions of the racemic dibromo acid (5 g. in 50 c.c.) and brucine (5 g. in 25 c.c.) was kept in the refrigerator. The brucine salt of the *laevo*-acid separated completely after 7 hours as a crystalline powder which was washed with alcohol and crystallised several times with hot alcohol, m.p. 211°. (Found: N, 4.95. $C_{58}H_{64}O_{13}N_4Br_2$ requires N, 4.8 per cent.).

The precipitate of the *laevo*-acid obtained by decomposing the brucine salt with hydrochloric acid (20 c.c. of 15 p. c.) was washed with dilute hydrochloric acid until the filtrate gave no coloration with warm mercurous nitrate solution. It was then freed from acid by washing with water and was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 123-25°, yield 2.3 g.

The *laevo*-acid (2 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (50 g.) and the optical rotation of the solution was determined at 27° by using red monochromatic light. ($l=20$ cm. $\alpha=9.37^\circ$, $M_{D100}=46.37^\circ$).

4-p-Hydroxyphenyl-2:6-dihydroxypyridine.

(a) *The semiammonium salt of the corresponding glutaconic acid.*—Pure powdered β -4-hydroxyphenylglutaconic acid (12 g.) was dissolved in ammonia (50 c.c. of 25 p. c.) and the excess of ammonia boiled off. The solution was boiled with animal charcoal, filtered and the filtrate evaporated to dryness on a water-bath; yellow crystals from alcohol, yield 13.5 g. (Found: N, 5.91. $C_{11}H_{13}O_5N$ requires N, 5.85 per cent.).

(b) *The pyridine derivative.*—The dry ammonium salt (8.5 g.) was distilled in a tubular retort under reduced pressure (40 mm.), the receiver being covered with black paper to prevent the oxidation of the pyridine compound by light. The residue was dissolved in alcohol, the alcohol removed and the residue washed with dilute alcohol and hydrochloric acid followed by a solution of ammonium bicarbonate; yellow needles from alcohol, m.p. 257°, yield 4 g. (Found: N, 6.93. $C_{11}H_9O_3N$ requires N, 6.89 per cent.). The compound turns blue on exposure to light and on melting.

Tribenzoyl derivative formed white glistening needles from acetone, m.p. 177°. (Found: N, 2.61. $C_{32}H_{21}O_6N$ requires N, 2.72 per cent.).

isoNitroso derivative.—A solution of the pyridine derivative (1 g.) in sodium hydroxide (10 c.c. of 20 p.c.) was warmed with pure sodium nitrite (1 g.) and the mixture poured into acetic acid (20 c.c. of 20 p. c.). The yellowish precipitate was filtered and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 194°, yield 0.11 g. (Found: N, 11.66. $C_{11}H_8O_4N_2$ requires N, 11.8 per cent.).

Sulphate.—A solution of the pyridine derivative (2 g.) in sulphuric acid (20 c.c. of 50 p. c.) was allowed to stand in the refrigerator overnight. The silky needles which separated, were filtered, washed and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 320-30°. (Found: S, 6.24. $(C_{11}H_9O_3N)_2H_2SO_4$ requires S, 6.35 per cent.).

Substituted Acetophenone and Phenylacetic Acid.

p-Hydroxyacetophenone.—An intimate mixture of β -4-methoxyphenylglutaconic acid (10 g.) and caustic potash (13 g.) was fused in a thick retort at 200-30°. The volatile portion was collected in a receiver containing ice and water. The contents of the receiver was extracted with ether and the ethereal solution washed well with water and dilute acid. Addition of petroleum ether to the ethereal

solution gave a product which formed prismatic crystals from alcohol, m.p. 105.5° , yield 2.1 g. (Found: C, 70.6; H, 5.81. $C_8H_8O_2$ requires C, 70.5; H, 5.88 per cent.). *Semicarbazone*, m.p. 189° .

p-Hydroxyphenylacetic acid.—The residue in the retort was extracted with hot water and the solution, after boiling with animal charcoal and concentrating, was acidified. The precipitate was again dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution and reprecipitated on acidifying the solution. White leaflets from dilute alcohol, m.p. 147.5° , yield 3 g. (Found: Eq. wt., 152.2; C, 63.2; H, 5.18. $C_8H_8O_3$ requires Eq. wt., 152; C, 63.1; H, 5.26 per cent.).

The following tables give all the compounds obtained with their characteristics and analytical results.

TABLE I.
Compounds from Anisole.

Name.	Formula.	Method of formation and yield.	Appearance and m.p. or b.p.	Calc.	Analysis, Found.
β -4-Methoxyphenylglutamic acid. (Limaye and Bhawe)	$C_{12}H_{12}O_5$	(i) Cond. of anisole with acetone dicarboxylic acid; yield 30 p.c. (ii) Methylation of the corresponding hydroxy acid. (iii) Thorpe's method.	White needles from hot water; m.p. 176° (decomp.).	Eq. wt., 118; C, 63.11; H, 5.19	Eq. wt., 117.9; C, 63.09; H, 5.28
The barium salt.	$C_{12}H_{10}O_5Ba$	Addition of barium chloride to the neutral sodium salt.	White crystalline powder.	Ba, 35.37	Ba, 35.15
Ethyl- α -bromo- β -4-methoxyphenylglutarate.	$C_{16}H_{21}O_5Br$	Heating the corresponding glutaric ester with PBr_5 .	Yellowish thick liquid; b.p. 246°/21 mm.	Br, 21.45	Br, 21.5
Ethyl- α -cyano- β -4-methoxyphenylglutaconate.	$C_{17}H_{19}O_5N$	Thorpe's method (<i>loc. cit.</i>) yield 45 p.c.	Reddish thin liquid; b.p. 251°/21 mm.	C, 64.35 H, 5.99	C, 64.5 H, 5.91
Diethyl- β -4-methoxyphenylglutaconate.	$C_{16}H_{20}O_5$	Alcohol and dry HCl; yield 60 p.c.	Brown viscous fluorescent liquid; b.p. 251°/19 mm.	C, 65.7 H, 6.88	C, 65.8 H, 6.74
β -Methoxyphenylglutaric acid.	$C_{12}H_{14}O_5$	(i) Reduction of the corresponding glutaric acid; yield 70 p.c. (ii) Method of Parkin and Thrope; yield 15 p.c. (iii) Kötze's process; yield 20. p.c.	White prisms from water; m.p. 164°.	Eq. wt., 119 C, 60.5 H, 5.88	Eq. wt., 118.8 C, 60.4 H, 5.78
Ethyl- <i>p</i> -methoxybenzylidenebisacetate.	$C_{20}H_{26}O_7$	Method of Kötze.	White needles from acetone; m.p. 116°.	C, 63.5 H, 6.88	C, 63.42 H, 6.9
Ethyl α -cyano- β -4-methoxyphenylglutarate.	$C_{17}H_{21}O_5N$	Cond. of cinnamic ester with cyanoacetic ester; yield, 65 p.c.	Thick yellow liquid; b. p. 177°/20 mm.	C, 63.93 H, 6.58	C, 63.8 H, 6.49

Diethyl β -4-methoxy-phenylglutrate.	$C_{16}H_{22}O_5$	Acid and alcohol with dry HCl; yield theoretical.	Thick colourless oil; b. p. 211°/18 mm.	C, 65.4 H, 7.4
<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl-isopropyl benzene.	$C_{10}H_{14}O$	(i) Elimination of CO ₂ from the corresponding glutaric acid. (ii) Reduction of the glutaric acid by P and HI; yield 35 p. c.	Liquid; b. p. 208°.	C, 80.15 H, 9.28
β -4-Methoxyphenyl-crotonic acid.	$C_{11}H_{12}O_3$	Heating the corresponding glutaric acid in a sealed tube with water; yield 40 p. c.	Rectangular plates from dil. alcohol; m.p. 156°.	Eq. wt., 190.5 C, 68.8 H, 6.11
<i>p</i> -Methoxyisopropenyl benzene. (Limaye and Bhave, <i>loc. cit.</i>).	$C_{10}H_{12}O$	Action of 5 p. c. HCl on the corresponding glutaric acid; yield 70 p. c.	White leaflets from alcohol and acetone; m. p. 39°.	
Semianilide of β -4-methoxyphenylglutamic acid.	$C_{18}H_{17}O_4N$	Heating the corresponding glutaric acid with aniline at 150°.	Yellowish leaflets from acetic acid; m.p. 184° (decomp.).	Eq. wt., 311 N, 4.5
4- <i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl-2:6-dihydroxypyridine. Benzoyl derivative of the pyridine compound.	$C_{12}H_{11}O_3N$ $C_{26}H_{19}O_5N$	Distillation of the ammon. salt of the glutaric acid at 40 mm; yield 50 p. c. Action of PhCOCl and NaOH.	Leaflets from acetic acid; m.p. 248°. Light needles from methyl alcohol; m.p. 163°.	N, 6.45 N, 3.34
<i>iso</i> Nitroso derivative. Sulphate.	$C_{12}H_{10}O_4N_2$ $C_{24}H_{24}O_{10}N_2S$	Action of H ₂ SO ₄ and NaNO ₂ in acetic acid solution. Action of 50 p. c. H ₂ SO ₄ .	Yellow plates from acetone; m.p. 201°. Silky needles from alcohol; m.p. 310-15°.	N, 11.44 S, 6.05
<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenylacetic acid.	$C_9H_{10}O_3$	Action of 30 p. c. H ₂ O ₂ on the corresponding glutaric acid.	Needles from dil. alcohol; m. p. 88°.	Eq. wt., 166 Eq. wt., 165.4

TABLE II.
Compounds from *o*-cresylmethyl ether.

Name.	Formula.	Method of formation and yield.	Appearance and m.p. or b.p.	Calc.	Analysis. Found.
β -4-Methoxy-3-methyl-phenylglutaconic acid.	$C_{13}H_{14}O_5$	Condensation of <i>o</i> -cresyl methyl ether with acetone dicarboxylic acid; yield 89 p. c.	White short needles from water; m.p. 173°.	Eq. wt., 125 C, 62.4 H, 5.61	Eq. wt., 125 C, 62.33 H, 5.54
Barium salt of the glutaconic acid.	$C_{13}H_{12}O_6Ba$	Ammon. salt and $BaCl_2$ boiled together.	White powder.	Ba, 35.58	Ba, 35.5
Diethyl β -4-methoxy-3-methyl-phenylglutaconate.	$C_{17}H_{22}O_5$	Alcohol and dry HCl; Yield 65 p. c.	Thick brown liquid. b.p. 265°/18 mm.	C, 66.67 H, 7.2	C, 66.7 H, 7.15
β -4-Methoxy-3-methyl-phenylglutaric acid.	$C_{13}H_{16}O_5$	Reduction of the glutaconic acid by Na-amalgam; yield 60 p. c.	Small prisms from alcohol; m. p. 149°.	Eq. wt., 126 C, 61.9 H, 6.4	Eq. wt., 125.6 C, 61.8 H, 6.4
Diethyl- β -4-methoxy-3-methylphenylglutarate.	$C_{17}H_{14}O_5$	yield, theoretical.	Yellow liquid b.p. 257°/14 mm.	C, 66.2 H, 7.8	C, 66.15 H, 7.7
4-Methoxy-8-methylisopropylbenzene.	$C_{11}H_{16}O$	(i) Elimination of CO_2 from glutaric acid; yield 79 p. c.	Yellow liquid; b.p. 231°.	C, 80.5 H, 9.76	C, 80.4 H, 9.65
4-Methoxy-3-methylisopropylbenzene.	$C_{11}H_{14}O$	(ii) Reduction of the glutaconic acid by P and HI.	Thick brown liquid; b.p. 219°/19 mm.	C, 81.6 H, 8.65	C, 81.6 H, 8.58
Semianilide of the glutaconic acid.	$C_{19}H_{19}O_4N$	Heating the glutaconic acid and aniline at 150°; yield 80 p. c.	Short needles from acetone; m.p. 201° (decomp.).	Eq. wt., 325 N, 4.31	Eq. wt., 325 N, 4.25

Ethyl α -cyano- β -4-methoxy-3-methylphenylmethane triacetate.	$C_{22}H_{29}O_7N$	Method of Kohler and Reid (<i>loc.cit.</i>).	Viscous reddish liquid. Pungent smell.	C, 63.0 H, 6.92	C, 62.88 H, 6.8
4-Methoxy-3-methylphenylmethane triacetic acid.	$C_{15}H_{18}O_7$	Hydrolysis of the preceding compound; yield 20 p. c.	Short white needles from water; m.p. 191° (decomp.).	Eq. wt., 103.7 C, 58.1 H, 5.81	Eq. wt., 103.6 C, 57.95 H, 5.72
4- <i>p</i> -Methoxy-3-methylphenyl-2 :6-dihydroxypyridine.	$C_{13}H_{13}O_3N$	Yield 45 p. c.	Small yellow prisms from acetic acid; m.p. 252°.	N, 6.06	N, 6.13
Benzoyl derivative.	$C_{27}H_{21}O_5N$	Action of PhCOCl and alkali.	White needles from ethylacetate; m.p. 173°.	N, 3.22	N, 3.19
isoNitroso derivative.	$C_{13}H_{12}O_4N$	Yield 42 p. c.	Yellow plates from acetone; m.p. 217°.	N, 10.8	N, 10.75
Sulphate.	$C_{26}H_{28}O_{10}N_2S$	Yield 50 p. c.	Flat needles; m.p. above 320°.	S, 5.73	S, 5.7
4-Hydroxy-3-methylacetophenone.	$C_{10}H_{12}O_2$	Fusion of the glutaconic acid with KOH; yield 30 p. c.	Yellowish needles; m.p. 109°.	C, 73.2 H, 7.32	C, 73.0 H, 7.25
4-Methoxy-3-methylphenylacetic acid.	$C_{10}H_{12}O_3$	Action of H ₂ O ₂ on the glutaconic acid; yield 25 p. c.	Prismatic needles from water; m.p. 128°.	Eq. wt., 180	Eq. wt., 178.8
Dibromide of the glutaconic acid.	$C_{13}H_{14}O_6Br_2$	Bromination in acetic acid sol; yield 75 p. c.	Leaflets from chloroform; m.p. 286°.	Br, 39.72	Br, 39.9

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